

HARMFUL PROPERTIES OF BORROWED WORDS**Ganira Askerova***PhD in Philology, Associate Professor**Department of Azerbaijani Linguistics, Faculty of History and Philology, Nakhchivan State University, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan, <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7756-8029>***Abstract**

Language is an integral part of the people's spiritual wealth, historical memory and identity. Language is the most valuable tool in understanding the world, expressing thoughts and feelings. Although the Azerbaijani language has been exposed to many foreign influences for centuries, it has preserved its rich and original structure as much as possible. The protection of the native language is the duty of every person, especially the intellectual, and the state has a legal basis in this direction. Every citizen of Azerbaijan should guard the purity of the language and give preference to using national Azerbaijani words. However, in the modern era, against the background of globalization and the development of information technologies, the increase in borrowed words from various languages, especially Russian and English, has a negative impact on the purity and development of the language. The article dedicated to this problem analyzes the impact of borrowed words on our national identity and language system on scientific grounds. Of course, it is natural that borrowed words enter our language to a certain extent, but their inappropriate use and suppression of national words damage the purity, richness and national spirit of the Azerbaijani language. In addition, borrowed words do not always correspond to the grammatical features of the Azerbaijani language. This affects the morphological and syntactic structure of the language. Language is the soul of the nation, the most important indicator of its identity and cultural heritage. During the historical development of each nation, certain words from other languages have entered its language. Although in some cases this process is perceived as a natural and necessary result, the excessive use of borrowed words can seriously harm the purity, functional capabilities and cultural uniqueness of the national language. In the historical development of the Azerbaijani language, words from Arabic, Persian, Russian and other languages have also entered our language at different times. Currently, a large number of lexical and grammatical units from English are massively entering our language. In this regard, the article examines the damage caused by borrowed words to the Azerbaijani language from a theoretical perspective, refers to existing language policy and legislative acts, the opinions of various linguists, and suggests ways to solve the problem.

Keywords: language, lexicon, borrowed word, language protection, law.

INTRODUCTION

Language plays an important role in the life of every nation. The languages of the world are in constant development and they continuously influence one another. As a result of this interaction, words pass from one language to another; that is, borrowed words gain a certain position in the lexicon of the receiving language. The influence of borrowed words primarily changes the lexical structure of a language and weakens the internal developmental potential of the native tongue. While such words, on the one hand, create conditions for the enrichment of languages, on the other hand, they also bring certain disadvantages. Especially from the standpoint of preserving the purity of our mother tongue, the excessive use of borrowed words is undesirable.

Language is not merely a means of communication; it is the most important indicator that expresses a nation's culture, history, traditions, and identity. Every language conveys the values, beliefs, knowledge, and worldview of its speakers. However, with globalization, migration, and the dominance of several major languages, many of the world's languages are facing the threat of extinction. At present, there is a need to study the importance of language preservation, the dangers faced by endangered languages, and the strategies that can be used to protect linguistic diversity. Today, the process of rapid decline in linguistic diversity is taking place worldwide. According to UNESCO, approximately half of the more than 7,000 languages spoken in the world are

under threat. Preserving languages is essential for maintaining humanity's cultural and intellectual wealth. Language preservation also supports human rights. The right to use one's language is recognized in various international declarations and conventions, including the Universal Declaration of Linguistic Rights. When people are deprived of the opportunity to use their languages in public life, education, and governance, they are deprived of their rights and agency. Currently, preserving the Azerbaijani language — whose lexical composition includes countless borrowings — in terms of its national character remains an important and pressing issue.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

In the study, the method of comparison and analysis of the views of various linguist scholars was employed in order to confirm the harmful characteristics of borrowed words and to present different approaches to the issue. As research material, reference was made to scientific-theoretical opinions and legal state documents.

DISCUSSION

The Azerbaijani language is among the languages possessing an ancient history and interesting developmental characteristics. "This language is the second language of the Talysh, Tats, Lezgins, Ingiloy, Udis, Khinalugs and other ethnic minorities living in the Republic of Azerbaijan, and serves as a means of interethnic communication for many Georgians and

Russians in our republic” (Hajiyev, 2012, p. 40). Our language has always been in development from the period of its emergence up to the present day.

“When we speak of the development of a language, we mean the regular change and enrichment of the sounds, words, word combinations, affixes, grammatical relations that constitute the structure of the language, and the elements belonging to its various components” (Sultanova, 2020, p. 124).

In this process, naturally, foreign languages have had a certain degree of influence. As the prominent Russian scholar Serebrennikov stated, the development of a language has two aspects: the development of the language under the influence of the external environment and the internal development of the language. In the evolution of any language, these factors are closely interconnected (Serebrennikov, 1970, p. 198).

As languages pass through historical periods, the phenomenon of the enrichment of vocabulary occurs. At this time, the emergence of new concepts requires the formation of new lexicon. “Language is the main means of transmitting accumulated knowledge and information to the next generation. Social and socio-political changes occurring in society develop the language. New words and word combinations formed in the language emerge as expressions of newly formed concepts in society” (Nagisoylu, Sadigova, 2020, p. 10).

This process is accompanied not only by the creation of native words but also by the transfer of words and expressions from other languages into the language. A. Gurbanov, who holds a special place in Azerbaijani linguistics, notes that words pass from one language to another under various conditions and at different times, for different reasons and through a number of ways, and he identifies three such paths:

2. Borrowings through literary and spoken language.

3. Mediated and direct borrowings (Qurbanov, 2019, pp. 225–226).

A. Qurbanov attributes newly emerging concepts related to the people’s development and cultural advancement to the first group. He considers words borrowed from any source language as “direct borrowings” and includes Persian and Russian words in Azerbaijani within this group.

“It is known that many foreign terms belonging to Eastern and Western languages are used in the vocabulary of the Azerbaijani language” (Cabbarova, 2020, p. 69). Eastern sources mainly include Arabic and Persian words. H. Zarinzade, in his book “*Azerbaijani Words in the Persian Language*,” noted that approximately 600 words passed from Azerbaijani into Persian (Zarinzade, 1962).

Borrowed words enter a language for specific reasons and acquire an important position:

- **To express newly emerging concepts** related to the development of technology, science, arts, and other fields as well as expanding relations, borrowed words enter our language: *syllabus, market, drone, computer terms, e-textbook*, etc.

- **They contribute to the enrichment of the language** and expand vocabulary: expressions such as *to send a message*, the use of *thought* instead of *idea*, *region, innovation*, etc.

- **The development and expansion of international relations** have strengthened the entry of necessary words — especially political terms — into our language: *reintegration, escalation, disinformation, delimitation*. The use of such adopted words reinforces mutual relations.

- **Borrowed words reflect the historical stages and cultural connections** experienced by a language. Words borrowed from Arabic, Persian, Russian, and English are the result of cultural, trade, and literary relations.

Borrowed words can be encountered in all the languages of the world. Indeed, “it is impossible to imagine a language that has not been influenced by other languages or that has no interaction with them” (Hummetova, 2020, p. 17). Linguists from various nations also confirm this idea. “The need for communication leads speakers of any language to come into direct or indirect contact with neighboring or culturally dominant languages... It would be difficult to find any isolated language or dialect” (Sapir, 2005, p. 268).

However, the excessive use of borrowed words harms the lexical and grammatical structure of a language. Currently, the Azerbaijani language has been subjected to unnecessary borrowings. Moreover, “those who sound the alarm about our mother tongue are right. Today, the Azerbaijani state, people, and intellectuals have a language, but they do not have the language of philosophers, that is, the language of thought. Nations that can transform their mother tongue into a language of thought are able to make distinctions. The enrichment of a language depends on written texts. The Azerbaijani language faces the problem of closure. There is a need to expand its boundaries and to transform it into a language of thought” (1). However, achieving this is difficult during periods of rapid growth in borrowed words. The excessive incorporation of borrowed vocabulary into a language hinders the natural development and purity of the mother tongue and, in some cases, violates the norms of the literary language. Especially in the contemporary period, globalization, the influence of mass media, and technological advancement have contributed to the increase of new borrowed words.

Article 5 of the *Law on the State Language* emphasizes: “In the official correspondence, documents, and statements of state bodies, organizations, and institutions, the norms of the Azerbaijani literary language must be observed” (2). The excessive use of borrowed words contradicts this standard.

In Azerbaijan, state documents adopted on language matters also prioritize the national language. The *Law on the State Language of the Republic of Azerbaijan* states: “The Republic of Azerbaijan considers the use of the Azerbaijani language as the state language to be one of the principal characteristics of its independent statehood; it ensures its application,

protection, and development, and provides a foundation for the national-cultural expression needs of Azerbaijanis worldwide in relation to the Azerbaijani language” (2).

Furthermore, Article 21 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, entitled “*State Language*,” states: “The state language of the Republic of Azerbaijan is the Azerbaijani language. The Republic of Azerbaijan ensures the development of the Azerbaijani language. II. The Republic of Azerbaijan guarantees the free use and development of other languages spoken by the population” (3). These official documents demonstrate that the national language in Azerbaijan has a strong legal foundation. The decree entitled “*On the Protection of the Purity of the Azerbaijani Language and Measures to Further Improve the Use of the State Language*,” signed on November 1, 2018, is aimed at preventing “the blatant violation of the norms of the literary language in television and radio channels, internet resources, print publications, and advertising media, as well as the noncompliance with phonetic, lexical, and grammatical rules” (5).

All of these measures justify the need to remain vigilant regarding our language. “This requires linguists to be active in both academic and public awareness efforts to protect our language” (Hasanova, 2025, p. 30).

Language data indicate that the active incorporation of borrowed words into the vocabulary leads to the following negative consequences:

1. **The purity of the mother tongue is compromised.** The use of borrowed words instead of their native equivalents creates confusion in the language. For example, in our contemporary literary language as well as in everyday speech and writing, we encounter synonyms such as *problem*, *obstacle*, and *difficulty*. In South Azerbaijan, the word *məsələ* is used for this purpose. It is a reality that, while it is possible to use the word *çətinlik* (*difficulty*), we tend to prefer the borrowed word, often without realizing that we are undermining the purity of our language. Similarly, instead of the word *proses* (*process*), the native equivalent *gedişat* can be used. As borrowed words replace native terms, the potential of the mother tongue is pushed into the background and gradually begins to be forgotten.

2. **National identity weakens.** Language is one of the primary means through which a nation expresses its national identity and culture. The excessive use of borrowed words contributes to the weakening of our national identity. When the mother tongue is not used to its full potential, attachment to national values and traditions diminishes. The influx of foreign words into the mother tongue leads a people away from their roots. The inappropriate and excessive use of borrowed words also undermines the original spirit of national literature, folklore, and traditional poetry. Consequently, the cultural values expressed through language decline. As the number of borrowed words increases, the ability to think and express oneself in the mother tongue diminishes, and national-cultural values are relegated to the background.

3. **The simplification of the language is harmed.** Historical evidence shows that as borrowed

words increase, the internal regularities of the language are disrupted, creating confusion in the lexical-grammatical system and word formation rules. This leads to a reduction in the richness of the language and limits the possibilities for expressing thoughts. Moreover, it becomes more difficult for new generations to speak and write correctly in their mother tongue. Sometimes borrowed words are used even when they are unnecessary. Native equivalents are forgotten, replaced by borrowed words, which results in the loss of the originality of the language and its artificial exposure to foreign influences.

4. **Negative impact on the grammatical system of the language.** Borrowed words sometimes do not conform to the grammatical structure of the national language, creating inconsistencies in its structure. For example, it becomes difficult to decline or pluralize borrowed words according to Azerbaijani grammar rules, which disrupts the natural fluency of the language. Consequently, grammatical rules are violated, and correct learning of the mother tongue becomes challenging. Expressions that are difficult for the broader public to understand emerge. In particular, young people and children face difficulties in learning the pure vocabulary of their mother tongue. In general, borrowed words do not fully adapt to the phonetic and morphological rules of the language, resulting in grammatical inconsistencies.

5. **Confusion and misunderstanding in the language.** When borrowed words are used inappropriately and excessively, especially among the younger generation and students, their meanings are not fully understood. For example, words such as *monitoring*, *coordination*, *innovation*, and *implementation* can be difficult for ordinary citizens to comprehend when used unnecessarily in daily speech. In contrast, the use of native equivalents such as *yoxlama* (*checking*), *uzlaşma* (*agreement or reconciliation*), *yenilik* (*novelty or innovation*), *tətbiq* (*application*), or *yerinə yetirmək* (*to carry out*) would be more appropriate.

It is clear that borrowed words, especially those that have been in use for a long time, cannot be completely eliminated from a language. However, it is possible to mitigate their negative effects. In this regard, the following recommendations are appropriate:

1. **Pay attention to terminology creation.** For new concepts, terms should be created by utilizing the internal resources of the Azerbaijani language.

2. **Prioritize speaking and writing in the mother tongue.** In daily communication, extensive use of native words should be encouraged, and Azerbaijani language lessons should be given priority in schools that operate in other languages.

3. **Conduct awareness-raising activities in secondary and higher education institutions.** Particularly among the younger generation, the richness and potential of the mother tongue should be promoted, and efforts should be made to prevent the inappropriate use of borrowed words.

4. **Consider strong language policies at the state level in mass media.** Special attention should be paid to the purity of the language in television, radio, and print media. Additionally, relevant institutions

should implement measures to protect and preserve the mother tongue.

Conclusion

The study has identified the following key points:

- The excessive use of unnecessary borrowed words, i.e., words that have native equivalents, undermines the purity of the language.
- It weakens national identity.
- It damages the grammatical structure of the language.
- It increases alienation and incomprehensibility in communication.

Completely banning borrowed words is neither possible nor necessary. The incorporation of borrowed words into a language in certain contexts is natural and inevitable for the development of the language. However, excessive and inappropriate use of borrowed words undermines the purity of the language, weakens national identity, and hinders the transmission of our mother tongue in its pure form to future generations.

Every Azerbaijani citizen has a responsibility to preserve the purity of the mother tongue and to approach borrowed words with sensitivity. Therefore, every individual should use Azerbaijani words instead of borrowed words whenever possible. Our mother tongue is a source of our identity and pride. Showing love and care for our language is both a national duty and obligation.

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